

The Serapeum of Alexandria

Secondary source

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* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Temple, Hellenistic Religions, Religious Group, Egypt, City, Alexandria, Religious Place, Archaeological monument, Religious Complex

The Serapeum of Alexandria, which contained the Temple of Serapis, was Alexandria's most important sanctuary and one of the most famous pagan sanctuaries of antiquity. It was also the center of a cult that spread widely across the Mediterranean in the Hellenistic and Roman periods. Ptolemy III Euergetes (reigned 246-222 BCE) built the temple dedicated to Serapis, the patron deity of Alexandria and the Ptolemaic kingdom. The site is located on a rocky plateau, overlooking land and sea. By all detailed accounts, the Serapeum was the largest and most magnificent of all temples in Alexandria. The Serapeum was part of a larger complex. The temple was inside a large precinct, surrounded by a portico lined with rooms. The precinct suffered a major fire in 181 CE. It was rebuilt and substantially enlarged. The Serapeum was destroyed in 391 CE during the disputes between pagans and Christians. After the destruction, a church was built for St. John the Baptist, known as Angelium. However, the church fell to ruins around 600 CE, restored by Pope Isaac of Alexandria (681-684 CE), and finally destroyed in the 10th century. In the 20th century, a Muslim cemetery, Bāb Sidra, was located at the site.

Date Range: 246 BCE - 391 CE

Region: Alexandria (Serapeum)

Region tags: Africa, Egypt

Alexandria located on the Mediterranean coast of Egypt.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Rowe, A. & Étienne, D., "Discovery of the Famous Temple and Enclosure of Serapis at Alexandria", in *Annales Du Service Des Antiquités De L'égypte. Supplément, Cahier no. 2*, Le Caire, 1946.
- Source 2: Fraser, P.M., *Ptolemaic Alexandria*, Oxford, 1973.
- Source 3: McKenzie, J. et al., "Reconstructing the Serapeum in Alexandria from the Archeological Evidence", *The Journal of Roman Studies* 94, 2004, pp. 73-121.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.bibalex.org/alexmed/projects/Details.aspx?ID=5036d643-6d40-4c7f-a189-e7a2331101ca>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1894-1896: Botti / 1898-1902: Sieglin Expedition / 1941-1942: Rowe

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: For the 1894-1896: Botti see Botti, G., *L'Acropole d'Alexandrie et le Serapeum d'après Aphthonius et les fouilles*, 1895, pp. 16-27 with plan; Botti, G., *Fouilles à la colonne*, 1896; Botti, G., *Plan du quartier "Rhacotis" dans l'Alexandrie romaine*, 1897, plan (with area of excavations marked); Botti, G., "Additions au 'Plan de la ville d'Alexandrie etc.'", *Bulletin de la Société d'archéologie d'Alexandrie* I, 1898: pp. 49-51. For the 1898-1902: Soeglin Expedition see Sabottka, M., *Das Serapeum in Alexandria* vol. 1, Berlin, 1985, pp. 7-14; Grimm, G., "City planning", in K. Gamma (ed.), *Alexandria and Alexandrianism*, Malibu, 1996, p. 69 n. 7. For the 1941-1942: Rowe see Rowe, A., "Short report on excavations of the Greco-Roman Museum made during the Season 1942 at 'Pompey's Pillar'", *Bulletin de la Société d'Archeology d'Alexandrie* 35, 1941-1942, pp. 124-161; Rowe, A. & Rees, B.R., "A contribution of the archaeology to the Western Desert: IV. The Great Serapeum of Alexandria", *BullJ RylandsLib* 39.2, 1957, pp. 485-520.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: It was incorporated into the urban plan of the city.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Diocletian's Column ('Pompey's Pillar')

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: In 391 CE, when Christianity had become the official state religion of the Roman Empire, the Serapeum was finally closed and destroyed in the conflict between the Christians and the pagans.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

Notes: A powerful earthquake and a resulting tsunami struck the city on July 21, AD 365. Despite buildings leveled along the shore, and ships at Alexandria reputedly washed onto the top of buildings, the ancient sources do not otherwise speak of any damage to specific buildings, even to the Caesareum, situated on the eastern shore of the harbor. (Ammianus Marcellinus, Roman History XXVI.10.15-19).

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: The principal Ptolemaic temple was burnt down in 181 CE and rebuilt again larger than before during the Roman period. In 391 CE, when Christianity had become the official state religion of the Roman Empire, the Serapeum was finally closed and destroyed in the conflict between the Christians and the pagans. Two churches were built on the site.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The main deity was Sarapis.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Isis, Harpocrates.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The main structures in the Serapeum that were built for Alexandria's Serapean cultists, were commissioned by Ptolemy III somewhere during his reign between 247 and 221 BC.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Notes: The temple's design is usually attributed to the architect Parmeniscus. As for the group, a probable answer would be builders and contractors since no building inscriptions explicitly name contractors.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: Ptolemy III financed the construction project at the Serapeum. The foundation plaques indicates that temple was built by Ptolemy III "King Ptolemy, son of Ptolemy and Arsinoe, the Brother Gods, [dedicates] to Serapis the temple (naos) and the sacred enclosure (temenos)".

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Serapeum complex included the temple of Serapis and Isis, a staircase building, a colonnaded court, a T-shaped building (Surrounding the Entrance to the Underground Passages), a Stoa-like structure, the shrine of Isis, the shrine of Sarapis, the temenos of the Serapeum, the altar of Ptolemy II Philadelphus and Arsinoe (during the Ptolemaic period), the Harpocrates temple of Ptolemy IV Philopator (during the Ptolemaic period), the Nilometer, the Serapeum temple library. Coming here to worship, Serapis would place his temple above the other buildings in the hierarchy. During the Christian period, and following the destruction of the main temple, two churches were built inside the complex, while the Nilometer moved away.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Diocletian's Column ('Pompey's Pillar'), the only monument today at the site, stands some 26.85 m, including its base and capital, and initially would have supported a statue some 7 m tall.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Architectural fragments were excavated at the site in c. 1900. These include Ptolemaic ionic capital, Roman and byzantine capitals, Egyptian capitals, and Egyptian-style statues.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Fifteen blocks that were found at the site are of the size appropriate to interior orders and some have extensive remains of paint.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: One statue of Serapis and one black stone statue of Apis bull (the last one was found in the sanctuary and moved to the Graeco-Roman Museum of Alexandria)

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A pair of red granite sphinxes.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Black stone statue of APIS bull and a pair of red granite sphinxes.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A pair of red granite sphinxes.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Ten foundation plaques, inscribed in Greek and hieroglyphs, were found in each

of the southeast and south-west corners of the temenos.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: The cult statue of Serapis was a draped figure with a beard seated on a throne, with a bushel (kalathos) on his head and a scepter in his raised left hand. Beside him was Cerberus, the three-headed dog of the Underworld.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Serapis, Isis, Harpocrates, Apis bull

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Some inscriptions commemorate the foundation of the temple.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Black stone statue of Apis bull and a pair of red granite sphinxes.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Serapis, Isis, Harpocrates.

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Serapis was not only a Sun god, but also a god of healing and of fertility.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Probably yes, in specific events.

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Probably yes, in specific events.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Bulls, geese, and other animals.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Yearly
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Yes [specify]: Bulls, geese, and other animals
- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No
- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: There are people bearing specific titles, who would be in charge of specific activities.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes

Notes: See also the comments on building phases.

- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - field doesn't know

- ↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
 - No

- ↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
 - Yes

- ↳ Birth
 - Yes

Notes: The temple was known for its fertility rites, and many couples came to it to pray for children.

- ↳ Transition to adulthood
 - No

- ↳ Death
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: The Serapeum was known for its healing powers, and many people

came to the temple to seek cures for their ailments.

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: Probably in one of the auxiliary buildings.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Large festivals held yearly in honor of Serapis, the Serapia on 26 Khoiak (22 December) and the Serapis on 30 Pharmuthi (25 April).

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
 - Notes: It would be included in some festivals.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

- Elites
- Non-elites
- Religious professionals

Notes: Probably.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- Yes

↳ Incubation

- Field doesn't know

↳ Healing magic

- Field doesn't know

↳ Cleansing

- Field doesn't know

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Expiation

- Field doesn't know

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably one of the auxiliary structures next to the temples could have such a role, but this cannot be proven.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The temple had a library.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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